

METHODOLOGY OF USING VISUAL TECHNICAL MEANS TO IMPROVE QUALITY AND EFFICIENCY IN MUSIC CULTURE LESSONS

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Abstract: This article is about the relevance of technical tools, their use in the lesson procedure, the improvement of the quality and efficiency of the lesson with activities such as expanding the musical ability, worldview, imagination and free thinking of students.

Keywords: exhibition, QR code, information resources, audio resources, multimedia, karaoke, textbook, innovative technology

At the meeting chaired by President Shavkat Mirziyoyev on March 19, 2019, it was decided to increase attention to youth, to involve them widely in culture, art, physical education and sports, to teach them the skills of using information technologies. The new system has put forward 5 important initiatives to promote reading among young people and increase the employment of women and girls. By 2022, the development strategy project of our president New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026 has been launched. The principle of "Strategy of Actions - Strategy of Development" consists of seven priority areas, including the further development of culture and art, among other disciplines, and the improvement of cultural institutions and the material and technical base of objects.

In the last three years, more than 160 general education schools were built in our country. In addition, modern and innovative educational institutions such as Presidential schools, specialized schools named after our great scholars, and Temurbek schools were established. On November 26, 2019, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev adopted a decision "On the measures and measures to establish modern schools". According to the decision, the main parameters for turning at least 3 percent of schools by 2021, 20 percent by 2025, and 50 percent by 2030 into "Modern Schools".

Thanks to the honor of the President, general education schools were freed from red tape, they paid great attention to creating conditions for teachers to work on themselves, increasing their modern technical support, and using modern pedagogical technologies in the process of education. To date, all general education schools have been equipped to meet the requirements of the times, provided with national musical instruments and electronic boards.

The relevance of my topic lies in the fact that in music culture lessons, together with visual technical tools, new methods studied on the basis of foreign experiences, innovative technologies in line with current demand, textbooks, multimedia applications, IR applications, audio resources and various national instruments, European is to improve the quality of the lesson with the help of musical instruments.

Based on the national curriculum, textbooks and notebooks have been published, and multimedia applications, audio resources, modern manuals with QR codes have been prepared for students. In addition, they develop students' speech, build memorization activities, and help to build easy comprehension skills.

Nowadays, it is not only with the help of books, notebooks, or the teacher simply explaining the subject, but it is also necessary to use the programs and methods that are suitable for the age, ability, quality and education of the students. With the help of IR, students are taught to feel the music live. With the help of audio, students increase their free observation and listening activities. Multimedia helps students to imagine and understand the topic more broadly, musical instruments that are unfamiliar to them, the history of their creation, the lives and works of composers, and the feeling hidden there while listening to their works. They know and study them, their character, what influenced them in the process of creation. For this reason, a multimedia learning environment is being created and a lot of attention is being paid.

Karaoke is also receiving a lot of attention in our country. On the initiative of the President, in accordance with the decision No. PF-6260 "On comprehensive support of young people and additional measures to further increase their social activity", starting from August 10, 2021, among young people continuously. In order to widely promote classic songs, karaoke format collections were prepared and a number of conditions were created. Karaoke grounds were organized in educational institutions, cultural and recreational parks for young people to perform national classical songs.

At the same time, according to the decision PF-6260, from August 10, 2021, in order to popularize Uzbek national musical instruments among young people, secondary and secondary special educational institutions and children's music and art provision of schools with modern textbooks and notes with a QR code has been launched.

To sum up, at the heart of many of the works being carried out the noble goals such of designing on the basis of modern technologies, improving the quality of lessons, raising students to become well-rounded individuals, preserving our heritage and leaving it to the next generation, their becoming as qualified specialists in the future are considered.

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